

ACID HYDROLYSIS OF ACETAMIDE

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The kinetics of the acid-catalysed hydrolysis of acetamide has been studied in water and in mixtures of water and miscible organic solvents. The acids used are nitric and hydrochloric which have been found to behave similarly. Since the acid hydrolysis is somewhat slow, high concentrations of the acids have been used and the rate has been observed to go through a maximum as the concentration of the acid is increased. Replacement of a part of water by organic solvents has very little effect on the concentration of the acid responsible for the maximum velocity. Probable mechanism of hydrolysis has been discussed.

Taylor (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2741) observed that aqueous solution of acetamide, when hydrolysed by hydrochloric acid, attained a maximum velocity by an acid concentration of 3.6*N*. Similar results were reported by Benrath (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 151, 53) and Euler *et al.* (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 131, 107), although they did not investigate this phenomenon so fully as Taylor did. Kriebie *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2976) observed that other amides behaved similarly and that sulphuric acid also produced a maximum velocity. The present work was undertaken to ascertain the effect of nitric acid and to investigate the cause of this peculiar phenomenon by replacing a part of water by organic solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

Procedure.—The reaction was followed by estimating the ammonium salts produced during hydrolysis by Kolthoff's formaldehyde method (Kolthoff and Stenger, "Volumetric Analysis", Vol. II, 1947, p. 158) with a slight modification. An aliquot of the reaction mixture was first neutralised with 1*N*-NaOH, using phenol red as indicator. The final end-point was adjusted with 0.1*N*-NaOH. This neutral solution containing ammonium salts was treated with an excess of neutral formaldehyde solution and the acid liberated was titrated with 0.1*N*-NaOH. The method afforded excellent results when synthetic mixtures of ammonium acetate and sodium nitrate were analysed. The error did not exceed 1%. Carbonate-free alkali, prepared by Sørensen's method (*Biochem. Z.*, 1909, 21, 168) was used throughout.

Hydrolysis by Nitric Acid.—Dilute solutions of nitric acid do not oxidise acetamide. This was confirmed by hydrolysing completely a 0.1*M* solution of the amide with 3*N*-nitric acid at 25°, when the theoretical amount of ammonium acetate was obtained. Four different concentrations of the amide (0.05*M*–0.2*M*) were hydrolysed with varying concentrations of the acid. Unimolecular constants were calculated. It was seldom that any point averaged varied more than 5% from the mean. In any experiment the velocity constant recorded represents an average of at least six time intervals (in hours). The results are recorded in Table I. The maximum rate was observed with 3*N*-HNO₃. That observed by Kriebie *et al.*

(*loc. cit.*) with HCl was at 2.01N. This indicates that unlike H₂SO₄, which gives the maximum velocity at 5.0N, HCl and HNO₃ behave in a similar manner.

TABLE I
Acetamide hydrolysis by aqueous HNO₃ solu. (25°).

Conc. of HNO ₃ .	Unimol. K × 10 ³ (time in hours).			
	(0.05M).	(0.1M).	(0.15M).	(0.2M).
0.10 N	2.7	2.6	2.6	2.5
0.25	6.4	6.3	6.2	6.2
0.5	12.6	12.5	12.3	12.3
1.0	18.2	18.2	18.1	17.8
2.0	27.0	27.1	27.2	26.8
2.5	28.5	28.2	28.1	28.0
3.0	30.0	29.8	29.8	29.6
3.5	29.1	28.8	28.6	28.6
4.0	26.8	26.7	26.5	26.4
4.5	25.2	25.0	25.1	25.1

Figures in parentheses refer to amide concentrations.

Hydrolysis by HCl in presence of Organic Solvents.—Methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and acetone were used for hydrolysis with HCl. The water content in every case was 50% by volume. The results as recorded in Table II show that the maximum velocity occurs at the same concentration of HCl even on changing the solvent, except in the case of acetone which lowers the rate of hydrolysis considerably and gives a maximum velocity at 2N-HCl.

TABLE II
Acetamide hydrolysis by HCl (25°).

Conc. of HCl.	Unimol. K × 10 ³ (time in hours).			
	MeOH-H ₂ O. (50 : 50).	EtOH-H ₂ O. (50 : 50).	(Acetone-H ₂ O. (50 : 50).	H ₂ O. (100%)
0.25 N	6.9	7.0	5.2	6.6
0.5	12.5	12.6	8.2	13.0
1.0	20.1	20.0	14.0	19.6
2.0	33.4	33.5	19.8	30.0
2.5	34.5	35.2	18.7	34.2
3.0	36.8	37.0	16.3	35.9
3.5	35.3	35.0	14.0	34.0
4.0	33.3	34.0	...	32.6

DISCUSSION

Taylor (*loc. cit.*) attributed the phenomenon of maximum velocity to the formation of a complex of acetamide with unionised molecules of HCl. The complex was considered to be stable and did not hydrolyse. He also stated that H₂SO₄ was not known to form such a complex and, hence, it did not produce a maximum velocity. Observations of Kriebel *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) prove this statement regarding

H_2SO_4 to be erroneous. It is felt that even if acetamide combines with HCl , the compound formed will hydrolyse more or less completely in water because of its very weak basicity. Its calculated basic constant according to Pauling ("Nature of Chemical Bond", 1952, p. 208) is about 1×10^{-20} . p_{H} measurements made by the present worker also showed that even a large quantity of acetamide added to a 0.1N solution of HCl did not depress the hydrogen-ion concentration, when measurements were made immediately. Moreover, if a complex is at all formed then the maximum velocity should also depend on the amide concentration. This has been experimentally tested in the case of nitric acid and found untrue (Table I).

Kriehle *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) in their explanation state that with a large increase in acid concentration, the activity of water falls which consequently lowers the velocity constant. The hydrolysis carried out in organic solvents like methyl and ethyl alcohol does not bear out this argument, because even on replacing half of the water by the solvent, the velocity constant practically remains unchanged. Hautzsch and Geidel (*Der.*, 1931, **64B**, 667) claim that acetamide is a dimer existing in two forms: $\text{CH}_3\text{CO.NH}_2$ (amino) and $\text{CH}_3\text{C(OH).NH}$ (imino). The two forms are in equilibrium. According to Kriehle *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) the amino form combines with the excess of the acid, resulting in the diminution in the concentration of the imino form which, they claim, alone hydrolyses.

The recent observations on structure of amides (Pauling, *loc. cit.*, p. 133) show that it is improbable for them to resonate between the amino and the imino structures. The parachor measurements of acetamide, made by Shukla and Bhatnagar (this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 611), support the following structure ascribed by Pauling.

In amides the donor and acceptor groups are adjacent and so they resonate between the structures (A) and (B).

It is felt that the slight basic nature of acetamide is due to structure (A) and probably the structure (B) alone hydrolyses in the following manner :

The nitrogen atom under the influence of electromeric displacement becomes positively charged ; hence, one of its hydrogen atoms tends to ionise.

The resonance between forms (A) and (B) will be completely inhibited by addition of a proton to the nitrogen atom and the amide will revert to structure (A). In presence of a large excess of acid such a situation arises with the consequence that the concentration of the unhydrolysable form (A) tends to increase. Taylor (*loc. cit.*) has observed that nitrous acid, which reacts with the basic NH_2 group in aliphatic amino compounds to give N_2 , undergoes a reaction with acetamide only in presence of mineral acids and the rate of the reaction increases, with increase in the concentration of the latter. This observation also supports the view that with increase in acid concentration (HCl or HNO_3), the concentration of the form (A), which is slightly basic, increases. This form being unhydrolysable, the rate of acid hydrolysis diminishes.

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